

EDITORS' INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic forced us to change the 16th Annual Symposium format in 2020 – from a full, in-person Symposium to an online "mini-Symposium" – but in typical resilient fashion, the members of the LESLLA community gathered for a full Symposium again in 2021. The 17th Annual Symposium, held via Zoom on August 11-12, 2021, was titled, “Reconnecting the LESLLA Community in 2021”, and featured two live keynotes, 39 recorded sessions and roundtables, three coffee break sessions, and an all-LESLLA membership meeting. Presenters hailed from 16 countries: Australia, Belgium, Canada, England, Finland, Germany and Germany/Afghanistan, Iceland, Italy, Norway, Scotland, Spain, Sweden, the Netherlands, Turkey, and the United States.

We want to recognize the hard work of the LESLLA Board, who planned the 2021 Symposium, and Andrea Echelberger, Patsy Egan, and Raichle Farrelly in particular. This group navigated challenging logistics – from planning for participation from more than 15 time zones, ensuring access to session recordings across a variety of platforms, to troubleshooting connectivity and other technical hiccups for presenters and participants, and much more. A fortunate outcome of our online format is that, as of this writing, many sessions from the Symposium continue to exist online, and we encourage interested readers to enjoy the 2021 sessions again via the LESLLA website: <https://www.leslla.org/symposia>. The success of the virtual format has sparked new thinking about Symposium modality in the LESLLA organization: the 18th Annual Symposium was our first-ever hybrid event, virtually on Zoom and in-person in Tucson, Arizona, on October 19-21, 2022. Our upcoming 19th Annual Symposium (September 7-9, 2023) will also have hybrid options, again virtually on Zoom, and in-person in Barcelona, Spain. Expanding our Symposium modalities gives us the opportunity to make LESLLA more inclusive and to bring together all LESLLA stakeholders, including students and teachers, in new ways. We are excited to see additional expansion of the LESLLA community beyond North America and Western Europe and to discover how we can learn more from one another, growing a more global and inclusive research base to inform recommendations for teaching and policy in LESLLA contexts.

It's worth pausing to reflect on the legacy of the LESLLA Symposium and the Proceedings that emerge from these gatherings. We have been hosting a Symposium since 2005. To-date, that is 18 years: 2005-2022! During this time period, we have produced 15 Proceedings publications – 2005-2019. Prior to the 17th Symposium in 2021, the process for publishing the Proceedings was managed by the organizers of the Symposium. This meant that, depending on who the Symposium host was, the format of the Proceedings would change – sometimes a host university would help publish the Proceedings, other times the Proceedings was produced through a self-

publishing platform. Since 2019, the Proceedings have been handled by the newly-created Board positions of Publications Coordinator and Assistant Publications Coordinator. In the beginning, the Proceedings were printed and distributed at conferences. In recent years, the Proceedings have become digital or print-on-demand.

This issue of the 17th Annual Symposium marks a significant shift in the way the Publications team will create and publish the Proceedings for the LESLLA community. Specifically, in an effort to make LESLLA Proceedings easier to find and disseminate, we now subscribe to an open-source publishing platform called the Open Journal System (OJS), hosted by the Public Knowledge Project at Simon Fraser University. The OJS platform allows authors, peer reviewers, and editors to upload papers, track progress through review/editorial systems, and communicate manuscript progress in one centralized location. All readers can now access a searchable index of Proceedings papers. We are also registered with the Library of Congress, and every article in our Proceedings has its own Digital Object Identifier (DOI) number. This means the articles in the Proceedings – and all the knowledge about LESLLA learners contained therein – are more likely to be found when people use library databases and search engines. In other words, our voices as LESLLA practitioners, researchers, and advocates will reach a wider audience. Importantly, the open-access format of the journal ensures that access to the Proceedings will continue to be free for readers.

While we believe this is a logical step in the growth of our organization and circulation of LESLLA voices, there has been a steep learning curve in the set-up and implementation of this new publishing platform. We want to thank the authors, reviewers, LESLLA Board, and broader LESLLA community for their generous patience during this time of transition.

Enjoy exploring this new issue, which reflects a broad swath of expertise in the LESLLA field: health literacy, home languages and biliteracy, learner perspectives in L2 writing, oral corrective feedback, diagnosing bilingual abilities in the domain of literacy skills, portfolio use and self-regulated learning, K-12 reading research and LESLLA implications – as well as work that responds to the unprecedented demands of COVID-19, such as teaching and conducting LESLLA research during the early months of the pandemic.

This issue also includes two invited pieces that showcase two wonderful plenary sessions: *Pedagogical Translanguaging in Adult Basic Education* by Ingrid Rodrick Beiler and Joke Dewilde, and an essay from Symposium organizers Patsy Egan and Andrea Echelberger who reflect on Alison Phipps and Tawona Sithole's plenary *Hospitality through Languages: Pain, Joy, Gist*.

We hope you also enjoy exploring 18 years of publishing history on our new platform. We know you will join us in celebrating the many writers, thinkers, and change agents who have helped establish our Proceedings over the years. We end by recalling our mission in the LESLLA organization: “LESLLA aims to support adults who are learning to read and write for the first time in their lives in a new language. We promote, on a worldwide, multidisciplinary basis, the sharing of research findings, effective pedagogical practices, and information on policy.” With your support and engagement, we will continue to look for opportunities to strengthen this mission with our work on the LESLLA Proceedings.

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